

CHARACTERISTICS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS OF GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION In this article, the characteristics of physical development of students of general secondary education were comprehensively studied. It was found that physical development occurs differently in boys and girls of this age.

Key words: physical development, physical maturity, anthropometric characteristics

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General secondary school age development is one of the most important indicators of health. How well the child has developed is determined by periodic medical examinations in medical institutions or schools. Almost from birth, each child's height, body weight, and chest circumference are measured. The obtained results provide an opportunity to see the general picture of the development of the child's body. In addition, the main indicators of children's physical health are the following conditions: teeth, mucous membranes of the eyes, oral cavity, skin condition, the degree of maturity corresponds to the subject's age. Functional indicators are also important during the examination. For this, the vital capacity of the lungs,

It is aimed at the comprehensive development of children, taking into account the interest, talent, individual talent, mental and physical characteristics, cultural

needs of children of general secondary education age, and taking into account the formation of moral norms in the child, the acquisition of life and social experience. is a process. Development of physical education of children of general secondary education age, search for new ways to solve their problems, firstly, with the need to resolve the indicated conflicts, and secondly, the laws of improving the physical fitness and mental development of the growing young generation, it is carried out in connection with the need to study methodological and technical conditions.

Currently, the most common method of assessing physical development is the method of correlation of anthropometric characteristics (on regression scales), which ensures the harmony and proportionality of their combinations, defines the concept of "physical beauty". The most important sign of physical development is body length. Weight and chest circumference are taken as derivatives of body length. In a word, regardless of the child's height (except for the limit values - low and very high), weight and chest circumference should be harmoniously combined with this growth is important. It is this that is genetically instilled and achieves the physical beauty that exists in a healthy person.

Further development of physical education and sports in our country, formation of physical culture in the young generation is one of the priority tasks of the current educational process. It should be noted that in our country, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Education and Sports" serves as one of the important factors in raising the youth of our country to be physically and mentally perfect at all stages of the continuous education system. In this process, physical education and sports education, organized in general secondary schools, has its own place and importance.

Children of general secondary education age they experience tremendous changes mentally, physically, socially, and emotionally
13-year-olds of this period are insecure, 16-year-olds easily turn into cheerful, forward-looking charming individuals. General secondary education age during this

period of development, a child's thinking skills change dramatically for adults, his body matures, and friends and social networks outside the family become increasingly important.

General secondary education age
The characteristics of physical development in boys and girls are significantly different.

- Girls' growth spurts usually slow down, while boys' growth spurts begin. they may continue to grow until they are 18 or 19 years old.

Breast development occurs in girls, hips expand; fat deposits in the buttocks, legs and stomach increase, the menstrual cycle becomes regular;

In boys, the height and weight grow rapidly, the muscles fill up and the strength increases sharply, the voice thickens.

Physical characteristics found in both girls and boys during this period:

- They are always hungry;
- increased need for sleep;
- appearance of various skin problems

An example is increased sweating.

The following changes are typical for young people in this period:

- debating skills are improved (and demonstrated frequently and with great enthusiasm)
- thinking skills are improved:
- the ability to apply concepts to concrete examples begins
- learns to use deductive reasoning and make educated guesses
- learns to think through problems even in the absence of specific events or examples
- will be able to construct hypothetical solutions to the problem and evaluate which one is the best
- attention to the future develops:
- learns to recognize that current actions can affect the future
- begins to set personal goals (and may reject goals set by others)

- improves decision-making skills:
- begins to distinguish right from wrong independently and develops a conscience
- learns to distinguish reality from opinion
- learns to assess the reliability of various information sources
- will be able to foresee the consequences of different options
- may challenge assumptions and solutions provided by adults

To sum up, physical development characteristics of general secondary education students are different in girls and boys. In this period, playing sports is the most important guarantee for health.

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